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Trust in Political Parties in the Italian Regions

Between 2011 and 2022 it grew on average by 24.62%

Istat calculates the value of trust in political parties in the Italian regions. The data refers to the average score of trust in parties (on a scale from 0 to 10) expressed by people aged 14 and over. The data refers to the Italian regions in the period between 2011 and 2022.

Trust in political parties in Italian parties and regions in 2022. Campania and Puglia are in first place for the value of trust in parties in Italian regions with a value of 3.7 units. Lazio follows in third place with a value of 3.6 units. In the middle of the table are Calabria with a value of 3.4 units, followed by Trentino Alto Adige and Molise with a value of 3.3 units. Umbria closes the ranking with a value of 3.1 units, followed by Valle d'Aosta with a value of 3 units and Sardinia with a value of 2.8 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the percentage change in trust in political parties between 2011 and 2022. Abruzzo is in first place for percentage change in trust in parties between 2011 and 2022 corresponding to a value of +41.67% equal to a variation from 2.4 units up to 3.4 units. Emilia Romagna follows with a value of +40.00% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 2.5 up to a value of 3.5. In third place Puglia with a value of +37.04% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 2.7 units up to a value of 3.7 units. In the middle of the ranking there is Campania with a value equal to +27.59% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 2.9 units up to a value of 3.7 units. Sardinia follows with an amount equal to 27.27% corresponding to a variation from 2.2 units up to a value of 2.8 units. Below is Tuscany with a variation equal to +25.93% corresponding to a variation from 2.7 units up to 3.4 units. Among the last regions there is Liguria with a value equal to +13.33% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 3.00 to 3.40 units. Umbria follows with a value of +10.71% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 2.8 units up to a value of 3.1 units. Valle d'Aosta closes the ranking with a value of +7.14% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 2.8 units up to a value of 3 units. Considering the average value, we can verify that the value of trust in parties grew by an amount equal to 24.62% between 2011 and 2022.

Trust in political parties in the Italian macro-regions between 2011 and 2022. The value of trust in parties has grown in all Italian macro-regions. In particular, this value grew by 28.00% in the North, by 19.23% in the North-West, by 28.00 in the North-East, by 29.63% in the Centre, by 34.62% in the South, 33.33% in the South and 34.78% in the Islands. The data shows that trust in parties tends to grow more both in absolute value and in percentage value in the southern macro-regions compared to the northern macro-regions.

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Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. The data shows the presence of two clusters:

- Cluster 1: Sicily, Veneto, Sardinia, Marche, Valle d'Aosta, Abruzzo, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Lombardy, Umbria, Piedmont, Basilicata, Lazio, Molise;
- Cluster 2: Campania, Trentino Alto Adige, Calabria, Liguria, Tuscany, Puglia, Emilia Romagna.

From the point of view of the ordering of the clusters, it appears that the value of cluster 2 is higher than the value of cluster 1, i.e. $C2 > C1$. We can note that the regions of cluster 2 are very heterogeneous and include southern regions such as Campania, central regions such as Tuscany, and northern regions such as Trentino Alto Adige. Therefore we can note that the regions of Cluster 2 are heterogeneous from an economic, social, cultural and geographical point of view. However, these regions appear to have in common the fact that they have high levels of trust towards parties. The regions of Cluster 1, like the regions of Cluster 2, are also very heterogeneous. However, we can note that among the regions of cluster 1 there are regions that have a very high per capita income such as Veneto, Friuli Venezia Giulia and Lombardy.

Conclusions. Trust in parties grew in all Italian regions and macro-regions between 2011 and 2022. Specifically, trust in parties tends to be higher in the southern regions than in the Centre-North regions. However, the lowest level of trust in parties is recorded in the Islands. However, for a correct evaluation of the indicator we must consider that the values attributed by the population are still very low. In fact, the indicator ideally varies between 0 and 10. In the best case scenario, the population attributed a value of trust in parties equal to an amount of 3.60 units, i.e. well below sufficiency. It follows that the population shows a sense of dissatisfaction with the parties in the various Italian regions, even if this value appears to have grown, it still remains essentially low compared to the reference scale. The low trust in the parties among the population certainly depends on the bad management of the parties. In fact, party management appears obscure both when it addresses the dimension of internal management and when the parties become a majority and are therefore invested with the administration of the State. The lack of transparency regarding the methodologies that lead parties to choose election candidates and the ruling class could have a negative impact on citizens' trust in parties. Furthermore, the familism, clientelism and profiteering that characterize the management of the parties, especially in the case of winning elections, makes the parties perceived as closed business committees that are not interested in the population. That is, the parties are still essentially perceived as closed castes by the population who in fact express confidence in a vote of 3.6 out of 10 in the best case scenario, at a macro-region level. From a political point of view it is necessary to underline the failure of the 5 Star Movement in the attempt to fight the "caste". From a legislative point of view it is necessary to consider the lack of a law on parties which becomes increasingly urgent given the role that party organizations play in mediating between citizens' requests and public institutions.

Finally, from the point of view of the institutional structure it should be noted that democracies that have greater stability tend to have parties that are also stable. Think of the contrast between Democrats and Republicans in the USA which has lasted since the foundation of the State, or the substantial three-party structure in the UK, or even the German Social Democratic Party which has been operating since 1863. In Italy, among the parties present in parliament, the oldest " " is the PD established in 2007, the 5 Star Movement in 2009, the relative majority party i.e. Brothers of Italy was established in 2012, Forza Italia in 2013 and the current League, which is no longer the Northern

League, was established in 2017. Furthermore, these parties are joined by many other parties and small parties which certainly give the sensation of simple business and electoral committees.

However, since abstentionism is a worryingly growing phenomenon in Italian elections, it would be necessary to introduce a law on parties also to establish the activities or outputs that the parties should produce towards the population. In fact, another reason that could support the low trust of Italians towards parties consists in the fact that parties are perceived as useless organizations that do not produce goods or services of any use.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Appendix

La Fiducia nei Partiti nelle Regioni Italiane												
Regioni	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Piemonte	2,4	2,3	2,2	2,5	2,2	2,5	2,3	2,6	3,1	3,2	3,4	3,1
Valle d'Aosta	2,8	2,4	2,2	2,2	2,3	2,5	2,3	2,4	3	3,2	2,9	3
Liguria	3	2,7	2,6	2,7	2,6	2,7	2,4	2,8	3,1	3,5	3,3	3,4
Lombardia	2,6	2,4	2,1	2,3	2,2	2,5	2,4	2,8	3,2	3,2	3,3	3,1
Trentino-Alto Adige	2,9	2,8	2,5	2,5	2,8	2,9	3,1	2,9	3,5	3,5	3,4	3,3
Veneto	2,4	2,1	1,8	1,9	2	2,1	2,1	2,7	3	3,2	3,1	3,1
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	2,6	2,3	2	2,4	2,3	2,5	2,5	2,8	3,1	2,9	3	3,1
Emilia-Romagna	2,5	2,2	2,4	2,5	2,4	2,6	2,4	2,7	3,1	3,4	3,4	3,5
Toscana	2,7	2,3	2,1	2,7	2,6	2,6	2,6	2,8	3,3	3,4	3,4	3,4
Umbria	2,8	2,4	2	2,3	2	2,6	2,3	2,7	3,1	3,4	3,3	3,1
Marche	2,5	2,2	2	2,1	2,3	2,4	2,1	2,8	3,3	3,3	3,2	3,2
Lazio	2,7	2,3	2,2	2,4	2,3	2,5	2,7	2,7	3,2	3,1	3,2	3,6
Abruzzo	2,4	2,5	2,3	2,3	2,1	2,3	2,2	2,6	3,3	3,3	3,2	3,4
Molise	2,8	2,8	2,2	2,4	2,4	2,3	2,2	2,9	3	3,3	3,3	3,3
Campania	2,9	2,5	2,4	2,8	2,6	3,2	2,6	3,1	3,5	3,6	3,6	3,7
Puglia	2,7	2,2	2,3	2,4	2,3	2,5	2,3	2,9	3,4	3,5	3,6	3,7
Basilicata	2,8	2,6	2,2	2	2,4	2,5	2,5	2,7	3,1	3,2	3,2	3,4
Calabria	2,7	2,3	2,3	2,3	2,6	2,7	2,7	3	3,2	3,7	3,3	3,4
Sicilia	2,4	2,1	1,8	2,3	2,1	2,3	2,1	2,4	2,9	3,1	3,1	3,2
Sardegna	2,2	2	1,8	2,1	1,8	1,9	2	2,2	2,9	3	3	2,8

Fiducia nei Partiti nel 2022		
Rank	Regione	2022
1	Campania	3,7
2	Puglia	3,7
3	Lazio	3,6
4	Emilia-Romagna	3,5
5	Liguria	3,4
6	Toscana	3,4
7	Abruzzo	3,4
8	Basilicata	3,4
9	Calabria	3,4
10	Trentino-Alto Adige	3,3
11	Molise	3,3
12	Marche	3,2
13	Sicilia	3,2
14	Piemonte	3,1
15	Lombardia	3,1
16	Veneto	3,1
17	Friuli-Venezia Giulia	3,1
18	Umbria	3,1
19	Valle d'Aosta	3
20	Sardegna	2,8

Rank	Regione	2011	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
1	<i>Abruzzo</i>	2,4	3,4	1	41,67
2	<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	2,5	3,5	1	40
3	<i>Puglia</i>	2,7	3,7	1	37,04
4	<i>Lazio</i>	2,7	3,6	0,9	33,33
5	<i>Sicilia</i>	2,4	3,2	0,8	33,33
6	<i>Piemonte</i>	2,4	3,1	0,7	29,17
7	<i>Veneto</i>	2,4	3,1	0,7	29,17
8	<i>Marche</i>	2,5	3,2	0,7	28
9	<i>Campania</i>	2,9	3,7	0,8	27,59
10	<i>Sardegna</i>	2,2	2,8	0,6	27,27
11	<i>Toscana</i>	2,7	3,4	0,7	25,93
12	<i>Calabria</i>	2,7	3,4	0,7	25,93
13	<i>Basilicata</i>	2,8	3,4	0,6	21,43
14	<i>Lombardia</i>	2,6	3,1	0,5	19,23
15	<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	2,6	3,1	0,5	19,23
16	<i>Molise</i>	2,8	3,3	0,5	17,86
17	<i>Trentino-Alto Adige</i>	2,9	3,3	0,4	13,79
18	<i>Liguria</i>	3	3,4	0,4	13,33
19	<i>Umbria</i>	2,8	3,1	0,3	10,71
20	<i>Valle d'Aosta</i>	2,8	3	0,2	7,14

